

LEGISLATION, METHODOLOGIES
AND APPLIED SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF GIS IN UNDERWATER ARCHAEOLOGY

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Abstract: *GIS has developed to become a useful tool in the recording and management of data from archaeological projects. It is important for archaeology to have at its disposal an instrument that, in a very simple way, permits the display of information about the location, orientation, and position of artifacts in archaeological sites and the relation of these sites to each other.*

This work describes the importance of this tool in the relatively young science that is underwater archaeology, especially given that the use of GIS has extended to the various sub-disciplines within archaeology.

Key-words: *GIS, Underwater Archaeology, Methodology*

Résumé: *SIG développé pour un outil utile pour enregistrer et gérer des données provenant de projets archéologiques. Il est important pour l'archéologie de posséder un instrument qui permet l'affichage de information sur l'emplacement, orientation et des artefacts position du contexte des sites archéologiques en rapport à l'autre, d'une manière tout simplement, pour faciliter l'étude.*

Ce travail décrit comment important est l'utilisation de cet outil dans la science relativement nouvelle que l'archéologie subaquatique est, depuis l'emploi du SIG s'est étendu à des sous-disciplines de l'archéologie à tous les niveaux. Il est également prévu pour motiver d'autres archéologues pour en savoir plus à ce sujet, et l'utiliser dans de futurs projets.

Mots-clés: *SIG, Archéologie Sous-marine, Méthodologie*

INTRODUCTION

GIS is of great help in all areas of archaeology. It supplies a spatial component to the more traditional database structures, allowing excellent acquisition, recording, analysis and visualization of geographic data.

Underwater Archaeology is a relatively young science, but the use of GIS within it has increasingly gained more attention, because, in many ways, its use in underwater archaeology is more complex than in land-based archaeology. Underwater archaeology needs a more careful strategy of management, research and conservation on account of the impact both of nature and of the anthropogenic changes which are the result of coastal development and recreational activities.

Because of the relatively short time periods that we have that our disposal to recover material from under the sea and the problems of not understanding a site in its totality, the result of poor visibility, GIS becomes especially important in underwater archaeological contexts.

We easily see that, because of the environment constraints, data are perceived on the surface as a whole, unlike what happens in land-based archaeology where interpretation begins in and is still oriented towards fieldwork. This system is, therefore, the best strategy at our disposal for the spatial analysis of an archaeological

site since it allow us to easily perform inputs and outputs of cartographic nature, and this way perceive the whole context or even restrict ourselves to a specific area. These zoom ins and zoom outs zooms in and zooms out enhance our ability to interpret the archaeological record.

GIS APPLIED TO THE UNDERWATER ARCHAEOLOGY

Since the beginning of the use of computers in archaeology, the development of a tool that could provide software to manage the varied digital information became indispensable.

Underwater excavations provide us with enough information to warrant the use of an efficient digital recording system. Before the use of GIS, other digital recording systems such as the programme CAD were used. Nevertheless, they it was not possible to share data between them and it became necessary to learn how to use many different programs.

The first attempts in spatial analyses may have had their origin in the overlay of maps of a same area and with the same scale, and which combined several thematic and spatial information features (Heywood *et al.*, 2002: p. 176). With technological progress this manual process was transformed into computer language and it consists,

in its entirety, of four components: hardware, software, geographic data and the human operator (ESRI, 1995).

The importance of spatial analysis in archaeology, especially at the inter-site level, is part of the postulates defended by the proponents of New Archaeology in the 1960s. There was a convergence of these ideas, at least at a theoretical level, in the development and use of Geographic Information Systems (Fontes, 2002), which resulted in what has come to be designated as 'the first phase of GIS' (Matos, 2001: p. 9).

The term was first applied by Roger Tomlinson in 1963 in his work on the CGIS Canada Geographic Information System. The following years were marked by the emergence of GIS software models (SyMAP, CALFORM, GRID, ODYSSEY), where, at first, work focused on archaeology nature was done using SyMap to analyze and calculate trend surfaces of archaeological sites (Wheatley *et al.*, 2002). In 1973, the University of Birmingham organized the first CAA international congress, which was dedicated to the theme of Computers Applications and Quantities Methods in Archaeology, which came to set the foundations for the various national CAA congresses, including CAAPortugal (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2007). This congress contributed to the growing implementation of information systems in Archaeology, including the Geographic Information System. Also, in the 1970s, the book *Spatial Analysis in Archaeology* by Ian Hodder and Clive Orton came up with a methodology to be used in the application of such systems in the interpretation of archaeological contexts.

In 1978, spatial analysis using GIS technology allowed researchers in southern Greece to carry out several survey studies which integrated, at once, the different levels of geomorphology and hydrology (Wheatley *et al.*, 2002:18).

However, it was only in the 1980s that GIS began to be more generally used in archaeology in North America, this with the application of predictive models in resource management (Burrough, 1986). Since then, the application of predictive models has frequently been used in many other countries (Djindjian, 1998), not only in the intra-sites analyses of site contexts (D'Andrea, 2003), but also in the inter-site relations between contexts. In the 1990s the use of GIS in became more widespread, highlighting the increased use of the predictive models. The first congress dedicated solely to the application of GIS to archaeology was held in Santa Barbara, California, in 1992; a subsequent one took place in Ravello, Italy, in 1993 (Lock *et al.*, 1995). The application of GIS to underwater archaeology is, however, more recent; it first got to be used in this century already, notably in the UK in important projects such as the Mary Rose shipwreck (from 1545), the Cattewater shipwreck (from 1550), in Plymouth Sound and in Breakwater Fort, and in the USA in projects under the auspices of the Institute of Nautical Archaeology in Texas. The first one mentioned is one of the most famous projects in underwater archaeology. The wreck of Mary

Rose, an English ship that sank off Portsmouth in 1545, was discovered in the 1960s and it took many years before an archaeological project took place. The excavation was documented by means of the *Site Recorder* and the data and information about the findings and the structure of the wreck were added to a GIS in real time by means of an Acoustic Positioning System, as well as result of the details and descriptions provided by divers themselves (Holt, 2007). In this case, GIS gave the researchers a wider perspective on the data and helped in the planning ahead (<http://www.3hconsulting.com>). The Cattewater site provides an instructive example of data processing in an underwater survey and in an excavation one where GIS allowed for an accurate record and where there could be a correlative analysis of the data obtained right from the beginning. The system was itself developed in Site Recorder 4 (SR4), which has the basic functionalities of a normal GIS. This program also allowed record temporal events, giving an evolutionary perspective of events over time, integrating information from various campaigns of work done on site (Holt, 2007).

Also noteworthy is the work in GIS using ArcInfo and ArcView (ESRI) in Tel Shikmona, Haifa, Israel, on the Eastern Mediterranean coast, where remains from the Bronze Age (1500 BC) were first identified (Bremen, 2003). These studies focused mainly on a reconstruction of the shoreline, on the demarcation of the commercial areas zones, on the working out of maritime and commercial routes, and on the study of outside influences and of contacts with other regions, evident from the examples of material culture from the Persian period (538 BC-332 BC) which were found. In other to perform a more a detailed analysis with the data, geomorphological, sedimentary and bathymetric characteristics were integrated into a GIS as well as the behavior of currents and the coastal dynamics in Tel Shikmona, all of which contributed to providing unambiguous results, providing suitable explanations for the type of shipping and trade that was done in the time.

In parts of Scotland, Spain, and Italy GIS has come to be associated the management and protection of the underwater heritage. In Scotland a GIS-based platform aims to put in one place all information about known wrecks, and this platform includes information about the type of work that has been carried out, as well the strategic plans that were at the oaring of this work, which is particularly useful for inter-site interpretation (Oxley, 2001).

A similar system was implemented in Andalusia. The Department of Documentación, Formación y Diffusion-IAPH of CAS (Centre for Archaeology Subacuática del Instituto Andaluz de Patrimonio Histórico) developed a spatial system to aid in the protection of the underwater heritage this on account of the large number of known shipwrecks in the coastal area; in the Bay of Cadiz alone there are over 870 documented cases of shipwrecks from the 15th through the 19th centuries (Alonso *et al.*, 2007). ARQUEOS, the information system used, and which

possess a geo-referenced database of known sites, was linked to DOCUSUB (an information database of areas with potential findings), essentially performed searches based on documentary references in the historical archives, but later it came to incorporate findings that resulted from remote sensors and other detection instruments. These data were arranged in GIS, in conjunction with information about environmental constraints and human exploitation (the fishing industry, tourism and the construction work, both public and private), and they have contributed significantly to the protection and safeguarding of the remains. Apart from this, the system is particularly useful in that it establishes a relation between objects and the changes in tides, the dynamics of coastal winds, geomorphology, biological activity, among others, in order to come up with predictive maps of the risk of those areas, maps which will then be analyzed so as to create strategic plans to protect these areas.

The Italian – designed Archeomar (<http://www.archeomar.it/>) by the Dipartimento per i Beni Culturali and Paesaggistici, Sezione per l'Archeologia Subacquea Technique (Maritime Archaeology Section), a department in the Ministero per i Beni and Attività le 'Culturali (Ministry of Cultural Heritage), is another example of the management and study of the underwater heritage with a GIS application created with the purpose of recording, positioning and documenting works of value that lie underwater off the coast of Campania, Basilicata, Puglia and Calabria.

Everything indicates that today GIS answers the needs of a fully integrated digital data management system in underwater archaeology (Matter and Wats, 2002). If it is to function as a new tool GIS should meet certain requirements. It should be easier to learn how to work with it; data should be displayed and read with greater ease; it should be easier to extract the information from it; it should be sufficiently complex for a big project and sufficiently simple for a small project; it should allow for the possibility of archiving and publishing information (Holt, on-line).

Thus GIS in underwater archaeology could allow for the storage of information about an underwater site. As a tool it has the possibility of examining those morphological features that were introduced in the system, such as tides, winds, currents, and sediment transport. It is also helpful in the assessment of coastal features, of the trade potential of a site and the areas of potential shipwrecks. All these factors contribute to helping in the preservation of a site. Geophysical surveying in an underwater project is a fine example of the use of GIS. The results of geophysical surveying, once introduced to the GIS, and because they can be integrated with other data, will permit the location and management of underwater findings.

GIS can also be used to study underwater landscapes in prehistoric periods. Because sea levels were lower in the glacial period, one can analyze those landscapes that are

now underwater, and try to reconstruct and define their outlines. The data collected can be introduced into different layers in GIS, which can then either be shown or hidden in the map, thus permitting one to see all kinds of information (Breman, 2003). The programme is not limited to recording spatial data, for it can also record temporal events by describing when things happened on what their relation to a site was.

CONCLUSION

GIS is an important tool in the integration of multiple datasets, one that can alter one's interpretation from what it would be if it were based on the traditional results of archaeological research. It can also add to the already existing approaches, and it can supply additional opportunities to study and analyze data and information.

GIS in underwater archaeology provides us with a useful tool to document information and to manage the different data obtained during an archaeological investigation.

Data from different projects in underwater archaeological sites need GIS to help to define potential areas of study. There are still many potential projects (many of which we know from oral sources) to be embarked on, to be studied and documented.

The versatility of GIS resides in the fact that it allows the discipline of archaeology to merge with other analyses provided by such things as remote sensors. This multidisciplinary dimension, and the reliance on other scientific disciplines, will facilitate and will lead to an improvement in the quality of underwater projects in archaeology. The main purposes behind the use of GIS in underwater archaeology are the recognition of past landscapes which are now underwater, such as past coast line and settlements now underwater, the identification of possible risk areas for wrecks, the production of digital models of depth and the contextualization of wrecks in their past landscape.

What we have here is a tool that permits us to align the historical component with the actual geographical one. When it comes to underwater archaeological project, GIS can provide a single database that will integrate all the data and which will, in turn, contribute to our research endeavours and to the diffusion of archaeological knowledge.

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